

Chemical constituents from *Zizyphus oenoplia*

A. K. Singh and V. P. Singh*

Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi-221 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : singhak06@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-542-2367568

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Abstract : Four compounds, β -sitosterol, β -sitostery- β -D-glucoside, luteolin and quercetin have been isolated from the barks of *Zizyphus oenoplia* and their structures were established on the basis of spectral evidences. This is the first report of these compounds in *Z. oenoplia*.

Keywords : *Zizyphus oenoplia*, luteolin, quercetin, chemical constituents.

Introduction

Zizyphus oenoplia Mill¹. (Family : Rhamnaceae) is a straggling shrub distributed throughout the hotter parts of India, Ceylon-Tropical Asia and Australia. In Indian system of medicine the decoction of the root barks is used to promote the healing of fresh wounds and the fruits are used as an ingredient in the preparation of stomachache pills². A number of cyclopeptide alkaloids³⁻⁵ together with non alkaloids zizyotin (a triterpenoid saponin)³, betulin⁶ and betulinic acid⁷ have earlier been reported from this plant. Herein we report the isolation and characterization of two flavonoids along with β -sitosterol and β -sitostery- β -D-glucoside from the barks of *Z. oenoplia*.

Experimental

Dried powdered barks of *Z. oenoplia* (3.5 kg) were extracted with MeOH in a Soxhlet apparatus which on removal of solvent gave a brown gummy mass (85 g). The MeOH extract was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column eluting with solvents of increasing polarity. The fractions collected from C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (1 : 1), CHCl₃, CHCl₃-MeOH (50 : 1) and (9 : 1) on concentration followed by crystallization from MeOH gave respectively β -sitosterol (1) as colourless needles (58 mg), 129–130 °C (lit.⁸ 133–135 °C); luteolin (2) as yellow granules (20 mg), m.p. 321–322 °C (lit.⁹ 328–330 °C); quercetin (3) as yellow granules (24 mg), m.p. 309–312 °C (lit.¹⁰ 316 °C) and β -sitostery- β -D-glucoside (4) as crystalline solid (38 mg), 264–266 °C (lit.¹¹ 257–258 °C).

Compound 1 [β -sitosterol] : IR (KBr) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) : 3300 (-OH), 2980 (-CH), 1640 (C=C); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 5.35 (1H, m, H-6), 3.53 (1H, m, H-3), 2.49 (1H, m, H-1- β), 2.48 (1H, m, H-4- α), 2.31 (1H, m, H-4- β), 2.25 (1H, m, H-7- β), 1.91 (1H, m, H-7- α), 1.90 (1H, m, H-2- α), 1.88 (1H, m, H-2- β), 1.87 (1H, m, H-11- α), 1.87 (1H, m, H-12- β), 1.83 (1H, m, H-22- α), 1.81 (1H, m, H-23- β), 1.75 (1H, m, H-15- β), 1.73 (1H, m, H-25), 1.72 (1H, m, H-20), 1.66 (1H, m, H-16- α), 1.50 (1H, m, H-17), 1.45 (1H, m, H-8), 1.44 (1H, m, H-11- β), 1.42 (1H, m, H-28- β), 1.36 (1H, m, H-16- β), 1.35 (1H, m, H-1- α), 1.31 (1H, m, H-14), 1.30 (1H, m, H-24), 1.23 (1H, m, H-12- α), 1.21 (1H, m, H-9), 1.20 (1H, m, H-23- α), 1.15 (3H, s, CH₃-19), 1.11 (1H, m, H-28- α), 1.09 (1H, m, H-22- β), 1.06 (1H, m, H-15- α), 0.95 (3H, d, *J* 6.7 Hz, CH₃-21), 0.92 (3H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz, CH₃-29), 0.85 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, CH₃-27), 0.81 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, CH₃-26), 0.67 (3H, s, CH₃-18); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 141.0 (C-5), 122.2 (C-6), 71.9 (C-3), 57.0 (C-14), 56.4 (C-17), 50.4 (C-9), 46.5 (C-24), 42.4 (C-4), 42.1 (C-13), 39.5 (C-12), 37.5 (C-1), 36.9 (C-10), 36.5 (C-20), 34.2 (C-22), 32.1 (C-8), 32.0 (C-7), 31.9 (C-2), 29.5 (C-25), 28.5 (C-16), 26.5 (C-23), 24.3 (C-15), 23.5 (C-28), 21.2 (C-11), 20.0 (C-26), 19.6 (C-19), 19.5 (C-27), 19.0 (C-21), 12.3 (C-18), 12.1 (C-29); MS : *m/z* 414 ([M]⁺, C₂₉H₅₀O), 396, 381, 329, 303, 275, 255, 213, 159, 145, 107, 57, 55.

Compound 2 [luteolin] : UV (MeOH) $\lambda_{\max}$ (nm) : 252, 260, 280sh, 350; IR (KBr) $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) : 3300–3600

(-OH), 1650, 1635 (conjugated carbonyl); ^1H NMR (90 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 6.20, 6.61 (1H, d, each, J 2.0 Hz, H-6, H-8), 6.80 (1H, s, H-3), 6.94 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-5'), 7.48 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-2'), 7.52 (1H, dd, J 2.0, 9.0 Hz, H-6'), 12.80 (1H, br s, -OH, exchangeable with D_2O); MS : m/z 286 ($[\text{M}]^+$, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$), 258, 229, 152, 134, 129, 69.

Compound 3 [quercetin] : UV (MeOH) λ_{max} (nm) : 255, 270sh, 368; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3150–3600 (-OH), 1655, 1630 (conjugated carbonyl); ^1H NMR (90 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 6.21, 6.42 (1H, d, each, J 2.2 Hz, H-6, H-8), 6.90 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-5'), 7.25 (1H, d, J 2.2 Hz, H-2'), 7.29 (1H, dd, J 2.2, 9.0 Hz, H-6'), 12.48 (1H, br s, -OH, exchangeable with D_2O); MS : m/z 302 ($[\text{M}]^+$, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_7$), 274, 164, 152, 150, 136, 124.

Compound 4 [β -sitosteryl- β -D-glucoside] : IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3380 (-OH), 2930 (-CH), 1635 (C=C); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_3OD) δ : 5.34 (1H, m, H-6), 4.48 (1H, dd, J 11.7, 2.0 Hz, H-6'- β), 4.46 (1H, d, J 7.6 Hz, H-1'), 4.22 (1H, dd, J 11.6, 5.0 Hz, H-6'- α), 4.21 (1H, m, H-3'), 4.19 (1H, m, H-4'), 3.98 (1H, t, J 7.8 Hz, H-2'), 3.91 (1H, m, H-5'), 3.53 (1H, m, H-3), 2.52 (1H, m, H-1- β), 2.50 (1H, m, H-4- α), 2.35 (1H, m, H-4- β), 2.10 (1H, m, H-7- β), 1.97 (1H, m, H-7- α), 1.92 (1H, m, H-2- α), 1.90 (1H, m, H-2- β), 1.91 (1H, m, H-11- α), 1.82 (1H, m, H-12- β), 1.81 (1H, m, H-22- α), 1.80 (1H, m, H-23- β), 1.78 (1H, m, H-15- β), 1.77 (1H, m, H-25), 1.72 (1H, m, H-20), 1.61 (1H, m, H-16- α), 1.51 (1H, m, H-17), 1.50 (1H, m, H-8), 1.45 (1H, m, H-11- β), 1.42 (1H, m, H-28- β), 1.39 (1H, m, H-16- β), 1.31 (1H, m, H-1- α), 1.26 (1H, m, H-14), 1.24 (1H, m, H-24), 1.21 (1H, m, H-12- α), 1.20 (1H, m, H-9), 1.19 (1H, m, H-23- α), 1.17 (1H, m, H-28- α), 1.15 (3H, s, CH_3 -19), 1.12 (1H, m, H-22- β), 1.06 (1H, m, H-15- α), 0.89 (3H, d, J 6.6 Hz, CH_3 -21), 0.87 (3H, s, CH_3 -19), 0.81 (3H, t, J 7.4 Hz, CH_3 -29), 0.78 (3H, d, J 6.7 Hz, CH_3 -26), 0.76 (3H, d, J 6.8 Hz, CH_3 -27), 0.66 (3H, s, CH_3 -18); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CD_3OD) δ : 142.1 (C-5), 122.9 (C-6), 102.3 (C-1'), 79.8 (C-3'), 79.7 (C-3), 78.5 (C-5'), 76.1 (C-2'), 72.9 (C-4'), 63.1 (C-6'), 57.9 (C-14), 57.5 (C-17), 51.0 (C-9), 47.3 (C-24), 42.8 (C-13), 41.1 (C-4), 39.8 (C-12), 38.5 (C-1), 38.1 (C-10), 37.2 (C-20), 35.1 (C-22), 33.0 (C-8), 32.3 (C-7), 33.1 (C-2), 30.4 (C-25), 29.6 (C-16), 27.5 (C-23), 25.4 (C-15), 24.8 (C-28), 22.9 (C-11), 21.4 (C-26), 20.4 (C-19), 20.3 (C-27), 20.1 (C-21), 13.7 (C-18), 13.5 (C-29); MS : m/z 414 ($[\text{M}$

$163+\text{H}]^+$), 399, 398, 397, 396, 382, 145 (Found : C, 72.7; H, 10.2; O, 16.7. $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_6$ requires : C, 72.9; H, 10.4; O, 16.6%); MW 576.80. The glycoside (20 mg) was dissolved in MeOH and refluxed with 2 N HCl for 6 h. The reaction mixture was poured in H_2O and extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 extract on evaporation furnished a white mass which was crystallised from MeOH. It was identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison with authentic sample (m.m.p. and co-TLC). The sugar in the hydrolysate was identified as D-glucose by co-PC with authentic sample.

The spectral data of all the compounds (1-4) matched well with the reported data⁸⁻¹¹. Finally, the structures of all the above compounds were confirmed by direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR).

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